

The Important Role of Stories for the Moral Development of Children

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to present the importance of stories in building moral character for children. The research question is why children's stories are still important as amoral foundation for the children in society. Tentative solution is to prove that telling stories to the children can cultivate moral understanding and attitudes because children can easily remember the characters in the stories and so, they can be guided in distinguishing between moral and immoral, that is between good and bad, right and wrong through the behaviors of the characters in stories. Most stories also contain lessons in the form of the consequences of good and bad deeds. Descriptive, analytic and evaluative methods will be used to achieve the aim of the research. The principle of analysis will be used. This paper will contribute to the understanding that stories can be used as a way of teaching the children about the moral issues and lessons.

Keywords : children's stories, moral foundation, moral lessons

Introduction

The aim of this paper is to present the importance of stories in building moral character for children. People use stories as messages for children because the stories can deliver moral lessons and knowledge to children. The stories can be seen as social and cultural tools that proclaim humans as cultural beings, who share their experiences through stories.

Children's stories are not only for entertainment purposes, but also to teach lessons, the world, Nature, people, animals and most significantly about how to behave well through simple moral lessons. Therefore, telling story is often considered to be a crucial aspect of humanity. Human beings have a natural ability to use verbal communication to teach, explain, and entertain, which is why telling story to the children is so prevalent in everyday life.

As regards with children's stories, children can learn about the nature of animals and environmental situations and there are good opportunities to summarize human characteristics. Children's stories might be one of the effective ways to introduce values to young children and make children exercise their reasoning. Through examples of the stories they are able to reflect on their lives. Children's stories are good way of developing a sense of morality and knowledge of children.

1. The Rise and Development of Children's Stories

Stories like folktales, myths and legends are the cultural traditions of the society. These traditions have been a source of value education as well as entertainment in the rural societies, and they hold the essence of the unique culture and traditions. The stories guide the children to develop moral and sympathetic attitudes toward others.

The stories have no immediate purpose other than to amuse, but they leave a substantial by-product which has a moral significance. In every reaction which the child has for distress or humor in the story, he deposits another layer of sensational experience which sets his character more firmly in the mould of right or wrong attitude. Every sympathy, every

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dislike helps to set the impulsive currents of his or her life, and to give direction to his or her personality.

1.1 The Nature of Stories

It is impossible to trace the historical origins and evolution of stories to a particular time and place, but humans began telling stories as soon as they developed the capacity of speech. They may have even used sign language before speech originated to communicate information for adapting to their environment. This information gradually formed the basis of narratives that enabled humans to learn about themselves and the worlds that they inhabited. They were simply told to mark an occasion, set an example, warn about danger, procure food, or explain what seemed mysterious. Moreover, stories convey ways and means to solve problems. For instance, following the Jewish story, "In Your Hands", teaches the children the skill of problem solving as follows;

The young rabbi would keep a live dove in his hand, behind his back. Then he would ask the old man if the bird he was holding was alive or dead. If the old man said dead, the young rabbi would let the dove fly free; if the old man said alive, the young man would break the bird's neck with his fingers and present a dead bird to him. The young rabbi's plan was foolproof. There was no way for the old teacher to win this contest. This would finally prove that the old man was not as wise as the people in the community thought. The morning came and, as the old man and his students sat in the shade of a huge tree, the young man approached. The young rabbi waited for just the right moment, and then he stood up and spoke. "Rabbi," he started, "I have in my hand a bird. Is it alive or dead?" The old man looked up at him with a face that was serene, but also a bit sad. "That, my friend, is entirely up to you," he said. The young rabbi stood there for a moment. Finally, he let the bird go and sat down at the feet of the old man.

This in logic is a dilemma- the solution is by "escaping between the horns".

Stories informed human characters to action, to transform the world and make it more adaptable to human needs, while people also try to change and make themselves fit for the world. Therefore, the focus of story, whether oral or written, has always been on finding magical instruments, unusual technologies, or powerful people and animals that will enable protagonists to transform themselves along with their environment, making it more suitable for living in peace and contentment.

Indeed, stories emanated in prehistory from shared experiences, and this is still the case. It is through oral transmission that stories of different kinds form the textures of humans' lives. Children learn early in social contexts by becoming aware of the intentions of other human beings through imitation, instruction, and collaboration, and they contend that learning is dialectical, involves understanding metaphors and different perspectives in stories.

1.2. The Rise of Stories

It may be said that even before the dawn of civilization, primitive hunters would gather around the fire at the end of the day and tell each other stories, captivating their audience with tales of their adventures in hunting and in search of food. This end of the day gathering became an established routine for ancestors. Indeed, listening to stories can be a bright, creative

experience. The storytellers share some values with the listeners and in this way they have a very good relationship.

Since ancient times, people told their children many kinds of stories which may be classified as myths, legends, fable and fairy tale. The people teach the children what is right and what is wrong from the moral lessons through the myth, legend, folktale and fairy tale. It will be discussed how they are different in what fact.

The stories are usually set in times long ago, before history. People have always questioned the issues such the origin of the world or the cause of natural disasters.

The myths described the things that happened to people and the choices they made. They might be about victory which is achieving something, tragedy which is losing something, honour which is doing the right thing, being brave even when they are frightened, or being foolish and making mistakes. People might be heroes in these stories and gods and goddesses could use their powers to help them or make things more difficult for them.

Around the world, myths were shared by groups of people and became part of their culture. People have passed the stories on from generation to generation and through families. Some myths are told in many cultures, but with variations in the events or characters. For example, concerning the origin of the world, most cultures, tribes or groups of people have their version of how the world came to be.

Legends are also stories that have been made up, but they are different from myths. Legends are about people and their actions or deeds. The people lived in more recent times and are mentioned in history. The stories are told for a purpose and are based on facts, but they are not completely true. The purpose was to make the story more interesting and to teach a lesson, like knowing right from wrong. Like myths, legends are passed down from generation to generation.

A fable is another type of story, also passed down from generation to generation and told to teach a lesson about something. Fables are about animals that can talk and act like people, or plants or forces of nature like thunder or wind. The plants may be able to move and also talk and the natural forces cause things to happen in the story because of their strength. The children are especially interested in fables and fairy tales because the animals act like humans act in the real world. The characters of animals in the fables help the children know what is morally right or wrong.

Folk and fairy tales are stories written specially for children, often about magical characters such as fairies, goblins and giants. Sometimes the characters are animals. Although there are different characters in each myth, legend, folktale and fairy tale, they all aim to provide the children moral development. From these facts, children learn to know how to deal, communicate and behave with one another.

2. The Role of Stories in Society

The society humans live in today could not exist without the influence from past generations because human beings hand down lessons and knowledge from one generation to the next. Humans pride themselves on leaving a heritage of knowledge for their descendants to utilize. The tradition of telling story to the children facilitates this transfer of knowledge. As a result, storytelling remains to this day the single most important tradition humans participate in. The most important reason for this being that every story contains a lesson to instruct the children. Stories teach them to love, to forgive others, to be just and to strive for better in life.

The greatest stories ever told function as a reflection on the world humans live in and of both the goodness and evil present in the world.

A Story has numerous important effects on daily lives. It has been one of the most effective sources of inspiration known to children. Storytelling acts as a fantastic teaching tool, imparting lessons of life to individuals of the children. The value of story holds as a source of inspiration and as a teaching tool makes it the most important tradition mankind possesses.

2.1. Children and Stories

Children are important for society because the development of society depends upon whether the children are well cultivated or not. Early childhood is a phrase often used to describe the period of a child's life before the age of five. It is the most rapid period of development in a human life and is critical to a child's cognitive, social, emotional, and physical development.

A child's environment during their early years has serious effects on the course of their adolescence and life course. What happens during the early years is of crucial importance for every child's development. It is a period of great opportunity, but also of vulnerability. When the quality of support, stimulation, and nurture is deficient, child development is seriously affected. Good nutrition, health, consistent loving care, and encouragement to learn in the early years of life help children to do better at school, be healthier, succeed in the working world, and participate more in society. Similarly, the mental and moral development of the children should be cared by telling moral stories since childhood.

It may convince that telling story to the children is a powerful method, and there are several reasons to that. One important aspect is that telling stories is a natural process and whenever people communicate, they tell stories. Stories are much easier to remember than facts and figures. Stories speak for themselves, and each learner can get out of it whatever is relevant to them and links to their personal experiences and needs. This is one reason why it makes a lot of sense to use story for purposes of the children's moral development.

2.2. Children's Stories and Morality

Stories play an important role in all societies and stories are often a vehicle for transmission of morals and values. The use of stories can be valuable in the teaching of morals and supports moral development of the children through the characters of the stories. Josepha Sherman said that

Storytelling provides other growth opportunities, as stories help listeners to see through another's eyes and to share the protagonist's feelings of anger, fear, or love—all from a safe place. The Austrian-born American writer and child psychologist Bruno Bettelheim explained that stories are important to children because battling difficulties through story can help them face real-life troubles. Stories provide role models who show us how to face demons and overcome adversity.

Stories have the potential to fulfill the goal of stimulating the moral imagination as stories have the power to evoke empathy in children. Stories provide concrete examples of values in action that listeners can relate to more meaningfully than they would to abstract communication of moral principles. In fact storytellers can manipulate stories to encourage empathy to one character over another, depending on the context or the moral lessons.

The story is a medium that stimulates the moral imagination, provides concrete details that allow for the recognition of moral issues. Moreover, it cultivates analytical skills through the practice of problem solving, elicits a sense of moral obligation through empathy and emotion, and reduces moral disagreement and ambiguity by normalizing social values. To better understand the way these functions take place, it should be considered what it is that makes storytelling effective in the transmission of morals and children build moral characters from reading or hearing moral stories.

Story has long been used as a way of transmitting morals from generation to generation. It has been tested by time and scientific inquiry and has been shown to fulfill a variety of functions toward that goal. Stories can entertain the children and educate them. Perhaps part of the success of storytelling to the children as a means of moral education lies in the inherency of both storytelling and morals to human nature.

2.3. Children's Stories and Education

Stories also can be used for educational purposes. Stories can help to develop a child's literary sensibilities, and listening to stories impresses a sense of story structure into a child's mind. Stories aid in stretching vocabulary, and children who are able to tell stories often gain advanced verbal ability and an increased sense of self-confidence.

Stories are one of the oldest educational tools through which cultures have passed down values and knowledge from one generation to the next. Story is a means of expressing experiences, emotions and ideas in different forms of transfer and dating back to ancient times. Despite all the modern innovations, the attraction of a story plays an important role, particularly, in the field of education.

Stories essentially are dramatic activities which encompass the non-verbal communication of body language, gestures and facial expressions. Therefore, the students absorb these elements mostly without their being an item of specific focus. And best of all, the students enjoy the activity.

It is important for children to make up stories, just as it is important for them to hear and respond to stories told by other people. When children create and tell a story in their own or a second language, the language becomes theirs. Oral language is an important tool for the cognitive growth of young children. So, Ahlberg and Howard discussed that

In challenging and stimulating their child audience, these extend the invitation not only actively to engage and interact with literature as readers but also, in breaking down the barriers between the apparently definitive authority or "truth" of what is written and the myriad ways in which it may be told or interpreted, to become authors as well, with the courage and desire to tell their own stories.

With the increased use of the whole language approach to reading and writing, storytelling has taken on an important role. Students with experience in hearing and telling stories such as myths, legends, and folklore are eager to begin creating or writing their own stories. Stories are particularly important to children because they help children understand their world and share it with others. Children's hunger for stories is constant. Every time they enter the classroom, they enter with a need for stories. Using stories in the classroom results in enhanced cultural awareness through the glimpses that stories afford into other people's worldview.

2.4. Children's Stories and Culture

Stories also help to broaden awareness of other cultures. The stories reflect many traditions and help to familiarize children with world cultures. Culture is defined as the whole complex of distinctive spiritual, material, intellectual and emotional features that characterize a society or social group. It includes not only arts and letters, but also modes of life, the fundamental rights of the human being, traditions and beliefs. Defining culture, Prof. E.B. Tylor wrote

Culture is the complex whole which includes knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, custom and other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of society.

To a great extent, culture defines man and it helps to examine his predisposition to other men. How he relates with such other men in the struggle to liberate the environment is considerably determined by his cultural background. Culture differs from music, drama, or artifacts. According to the former, culture covers such aspects of man's life as norms, tales or laws that govern and control human behavior and beliefs.

Stories are windows open to the world. They bring in views about different people, new countries and diverse cultural values. Stories help children show a curiosity about other cultures, far-off lands and peoples from other parts of the country. Using stories can prepare children for openness, awareness, tolerance and acceptance towards other ways of understanding life. In this sense, children can gain sensitive attitudes towards others which will make them better relationships.

Even within contemporary stories for children, they can experience the attitudes and values of people from different cultures, from different regions within one's own country or from nations near and far. A story is a strong influence on culture and society. It is through children's stories that children learn about the knowledge, beliefs, and culture of people in all parts of the world

.Conclusion

Children's stories provide children with the opportunity to respond and develop their own opinions. They can learn to evaluate and analyze, as well as summarize and hypothesize about the stories.

Children's stories also provide a possibility to learn about their own cultural heritage and the cultures of other people. It is crucial for children to learn these values because developing positive attitudes toward their own culture and the cultures of others is necessary for both social and personal development. From the stories, which contain obvious stereotypes about certain cultural groups, children can realize the cultural values of that group.

Moreover, children's stories help students develop emotional intelligence. Children's stories encourage them to think deeper about their own feelings and also encourage creativity. Children's stories may promote the development of children's internal imaginations because children are very impressionable during the formative years, and stories can help them develop into caring, intelligent, and friendly people.

Children's stories can promote social development by encouraging the children to accept other people and their differences, and may encourage them to become more open-minded to different types of families and understand that love is the most important thing in a family.

In the field of education, children's stories are valuable in both the school and at home. and valuable in providing an opportunity to respond to literature, as well as cultural knowledge, emotional intelligence and creativity, social and personality development, Exposing children to stories can contribute to the creation of responsible, successful, and caring individuals.

It may be concluded that telling stories to the children has been playing an important part for the moral foundations in the societies. The stories which differ in content and quality involve various elements such as entertainment, education, humanity, and results of actions, and other issues. In this way, stories give the children a collection of values, beliefs and attitudes certain already set patterns of behavior. These cultural values open the minds of the children to their immediate surroundings in particular and the world in general.

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